

School bikeability index: A case study of primary schools in Stockholm

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ABSTRACT

In most developed countries, active travel to and from school has declined over the past few decades. In Sweden, active travel among children and young adults declined by 40 % between 1995 and 2014. To remedy and reverse this trend, it is crucial to understand and establish the necessary preconditions for promoting active school travel, i.e. built environment and infrastructural provisions. Within that context, this paper presents a school bikeability index for Stockholm, focusing primarily on built environment indicators. These indicators were weighted according to their importance as perceived by children's guardians in Stockholm. The study provides insights into possible correlates of importance of bikeability indicators, suggesting different valuations by guardians depending on their gender and children's age. The spatial analysis shows a variability of school bikeability across the city. Findings suggest that overall many of the primary schools could significantly enhance their bikeability by implementing measures such as, bicycle parking, traffic calming signage and connecting school entrances directly to cycle paths. Closer investigations of some of the highest- and lowest-scoring schools and selected school pairs inform that even the high-scoring schools are often lacking in implementation of some children-friendly cycling infrastructure, and that low-scoring schools could benefit from implementing some, relatively low-cost improvements. An equity analysis shows no significant differences between school bikeability scores and average income. Open access data were utilised, allowing the methodology to be replicable in other cities. For future iterations of the index, it would be beneficial to refine and validate the index weights while incorporating additional indicators. This process should account for their complexity and the varying valuations assigned by different groups, including children themselves.

1. Introduction

Improving urban cycling conditions is a widely acknowledged strategy for addressing some of the current environmental and health-related challenges, including reducing carbon emissions and increasing physical activity (Brand et al., 2021; Chillón et al., 2010). There is strong evidence that cycling provides additional benefits to children, such as improved mental well-being and stress management (Cerro Herrero et al., 2021; Gray et al., 2023), greater independence and self-efficacy (Goodman et al., 2016; Rutberg and Lindqvist, 2018), an improved sense of belonging and community (Pacilli et al., 2013), and better performance at school (Käll et al., 2014; Phansikar et al., 2019). Moreover, cycling to school helps establish a habit of active travel and physical activity, promoting similar sustainable behaviour into adulthood (Yang et al., 2014).

However, what has been observed across most developed countries in recent decades is a decline in cycling to school (Aranda-Balboa et al.,

2020; Ikeda et al., 2020; Kytä et al., 2015; Rothman et al., 2018; Westman et al., 2017). This trend is particularly notable in Sweden, where a study examining cycling patterns between 1995 and 2014 concluded that children's and young adults' cycling decreased by over 40 % during this period, and the number of school trips by bike declined by 48 % (Transport Analysis, 2015). In addition to social and behavioural factors—such as the desire to escort the child, the mobility habits of guardians, the convenience of car use, and lack of social support from others who cycle (e.g., peers, friends)—built environment factors, including the absence of cycling infrastructure, long distances, and safety risks have been found to contribute to increased driving to school and lower cycling rates (Aranda-Balboa et al., 2020; Hume et al., 2009; Kytä et al., 2015; McDonald and Aalborg, 2009; McDonald et al., 2014; Mitra, 2013; Rotaris et al., 2023; Weigand and McDonald, 2011; Westman et al., 2017). The relative importance of these factors may vary between regions. A longitudinal study from the UK (Panter et al., 2013) showed that improving the safety of school routes, together with

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reducing the convenience of car use and increasing the convenience of active modes may influence cycling to school. A Finnish study (Kytta et al., 2015) found that the most common reasons for picking up children from school were concerns about traffic danger and combining the pick up with another activity, and picking up the children from school was significantly related to family's access to a car. A study from Sweden (Westman et al., 2017) found convenience to be an important determinant of car use on the way to and from school.

Previous research have also indicated that municipalities, including those in Sweden, have limited financial resources and lack the political capability to improve cycling, resulting in many proposed cycling improvement measures being cancelled or postponed (Alm and Koglin, 2022). To improve these capabilities and allocate investment more efficiently, there is a need for a more systematic approach to the assessment and identification of priority areas for improvement. One method to assess the current state of bicycle friendliness is through accessibility or bikeability analysis (Lowry et al., 2012; Vale et al., 2015). Such analyses, often in the form of a bikeability index, provide insights into potential barriers and indicate areas in need of improvement (Munira et al., 2021). Previous studies have provided an extensive overview of existing bikeability indices. The two latest reviews focusing on bikeability indices and their indicators (Castañon and Ribeiro, 2021; Valenzuela et al., 2022) both identified over 100 indicators across four to five categories, including cycle infrastructure, accessibility, safety, and surrounding environment or topography and land use. The most common indicators were related to infrastructure, such as the existence and width of bike lanes, followed by destinations, slope, speed limits, connectivity and intersections.

Most previous research on bikeability indices has not differentiated among specific user types, although some exceptions exist, such as distinguishing cyclist types based on the combination of cycling frequency and travel purpose (Arellana et al., 2020), differentiating between cyclists and non-cyclists (Motta, 2017), and distinguishing between commuter and recreational cyclists (Porter et al., 2020). There is a lack of studies examining children's cycling accessibility. Among the few, Robillard et al. (2023) developed children-specific (walking and cycling) accessibility measures to assess accessibility to parks based on the cycling network, which consisted of cycle paths, cycle lanes, designated roadways and public roads with a maximum speed limit of 50 km/h. The authors noted that cycling network may not be suitable for younger children. Rugtvedt (2019) developed a bikeability index that included school children among other user groups. The study applied the same bikeability indicators across all study groups (experienced cyclists, schoolchildren, people with reduced mobility and e-bikers) but it relied on expert judgements to determine the weights of each indicator for the specific user groups. The weights assigned to the children's group were, on average, slightly higher than those for the other groups. However, the comparison of the bikeability index results for the different groups showed little variation. The authors noted that the low variability could have been caused by missing data for some of the indicators. Another study (Goodman et al., 2019) modelled the propensity to cycle to school using origin-destination data for school travel in England. The propensity to cycle was modelled as a function of route distance and hilliness and can thus be viewed as an indication of cycling accessibility. However, the study did not consider the current state of the cycling infrastructure, and concluded that trip distance and hilliness alone could have not explained the low rates of cycling in England. A recent study that focused entirely on school bikeability is by Paulusová and Sharmeen (2024) where they compiled, based on an extensive review of literature, a list of indicators that matter for children's school bikeability. However, the study did not construct or operationalise a school bikeability index.

Children's needs for cycling in urban environments differ mainly due to their inability to cope with complex traffic situations, including challenges such as correctly estimating and predicting dangerous situations, dividing their attention, and not getting easily distracted

(Björklid and Gummesson, 2013). Further, in contrast to adults or youth who have the independence to decide on their mobility, guardians play an important role in children's mode choice, and thus their possibility to bike, as suggested by theory (McMillan, 2005) and evidence (Mitra et al., 2010; Nyström et al., 2023; Panter et al., 2013). For example, an earlier study from the UK (Aldred, 2015) found that while adults had a 76 % preference for cycling on residential streets without cycling infrastructure, only 25 % of adults would have allowed their child to cycle on such streets. Another study (Wilson et al., 2018) found that parental perceptions of barriers to active travel school behaviour had a greater impact on actual behaviour than children's perceptions, suggesting the importance of considering parents' opinions when evaluating children's bikeability. This is further supported by the fact that a study of five different schools in Sweden (Björklid and Gummesson, 2013) found that of those who own a bike, less than 10 % of children aged 8 and 9 were allowed by their parents to cycle on busy roads. This percentage increased to about 17 % for children aged 10, 32 % for children aged 11, and 42 % for children aged 12. Another study from a Swedish context (Westman et al., 2017) found that parents with older children valued safety on the way to school less when deciding whether to take the car or use another mode, compared to parents with younger children. This evidence suggest that it is important to consider children's bikeability separately from that of adults, and that adults play an important role in the children's bikeability.

To enhance cycling accessibility to school, and thus possibly contribute to reversing the decline in cycling to school, this study follows up on the previously populated list of indicators in Paulusová and Sharmeen (2024) and introduces a School Bikeability Index (SBI). This study uses the same definition of bikeability as Paulusová and Sharmeen (2024, p. 4), namely, "the ability of the urban landscape to accommodate cycling", and specifically to accommodate children's cycling to school. The scope of the study is predominantly limited to built environment indicators for school bikeability, without focusing on behavioural aspects of mode choice, travel choice or habit formation. The index was applied as a case study of primary schools in Stockholm. To reflect local conditions that are important for school bikeability, specific indicators based on local policy regulations were incorporated into the index. One of the expectations of this SBI was that schools in the same neighbourhood with presumably similar built environment features would have similar SBI scores. When this was not the case a detailed in depth analysis was conducted. Moreover, cycling accessibility has been earlier found to vary depending on an area's socio-economic characteristics. For instance, wealthier areas usually experience better cycling conditions (Cunha and Silva, 2022; Flanagan et al., 2016), whereas socio-economically disadvantaged populations are often left with poorer cycling conditions. Accessibility analysis helps identify spatial disparities in cycling conditions, revealing whether there is evidence for possible exclusion of children from socio-economically disadvantaged areas from cycling to school. To assess whether such differences in school bikeability based on socio-economic characteristics exist in Stockholm, an analysis examining the SBI in relation to income was undertaken.

The paper is organised as follows: Section 2 introduces the study area, the selection of indicators and the refinement of relevant indicators based on local knowledge to enrich the more general index. Section 3 describes the data and methodology. Section 4 summarises the results of the different analyses, and Section 5 provides a discussion and a conclusion.

2. Study area and local indicators

2.1. Study area and target group

The focus area of this study is Stockholms stad (City of Stockholm, hereafter referred to as Stockholm) located in Stockholm County. Stockholm, with a population of 948 784, is further divided into 13 districts. Each district is overseen by an appointed administrative

District Council responsible for primary schools (excluding independent schools) and other essential services. Sweden is considered a country where cycling already plays an important role in everyday travel (Haustein et al., 2019). Despite this, Stockholm lags behind other bicycle-friendly cities due to a car-centric planning approach adopted following the Second World War that has not been successfully reversed. For instance, in 2020, the share of cycling was 7 % in the Stockholm Urban Area, compared to 30 % in the Amsterdam Transport Area and 41 % in the Copenhagen Metropolitan Area in 2018 (Deloitte, 2019, 2020a, 2020b).

Numerous efforts to improve cycling accessibility have been initiated in Sweden in recent years. These efforts include projects and plans aimed at improving security and safety along school routes, such as the Plan for Safe and Secure School Routes ("Plan" hereafter; Stockholms stad, 2016), the development of a new national cycling strategy, and a revision of Stockholm's cycling strategy (Regeringen, 2017; Trafikkontoret Stockholms stad stad, 2022a, 2022b). Infrastructural improvements have also been made in Stockholm; on average, 10 km of new and widened bicycle lanes have been constructed per year in the last 10 years, 4 % of the city's street and road network has been reserved for cycle lanes, and the number of cycling passages in the inner city has doubled in the last 15 years (Trafikkontoret Stockholms stad stad, 2022b).

Between 2014 and 2023, cycling increased by just over 25 % in Stockholm (Trafikkontoret Stockholms stad stad, 2024). During this period, the number of injured cyclists in traffic accidents remained relatively stable, averaging around 980 injuries per year and accounting for 25 % of all traffic-related injuries (Stockholms stad, 2024b). Cyclist fatalities comprised up to 18 % of total traffic fatalities. Children represented 'the least common group' in the traffic injuries statistics between 2012 and 2021 (Stockholms stad, 2022b). Although they made up 18 % of the city's population, they were involved in only 6 % of all traffic

injuries and 2 % of traffic fatalities during that period (Stockholms stad, 2021). Among children injured in traffic, the majority were cyclists (42 %), with most incidents involving single-vehicle accidents. In Sweden, such accidents are typically caused by weather conditions (e.g. skidding on ice or snow), downhill slopes, loss of balance at low or no speed, and features of the built environment (e.g., potholes, curbstones, or road infrastructure design; Algurén and Rizzi, 2022). While children account for a relatively small share of total traffic injuries, it is important to note that cycling-related accidents among them still represent a significant proportion of these incidents.

This study focuses on primary schools offering any classes from grades 1–6 (approximate ages between 7 and 13). This group was chosen because younger children are more likely to live within cycling distance of their school in Sweden (Björklid and Gummesson, 2013). According to the recommendation of the National Federation for Road Safety in Sweden (Nationella trafikförsäkerhetsförbundet) that children younger than 11 or 12 years are not mature enough to cycle alone in complex traffic environments. However, the organization also recognises that younger children should have the opportunity to travel to school independently and that they might be allowed to cycle alone earlier if safe cycling infrastructure is available. There were 222 schools in Stockholm that offered at least one of grades 1–6 (Fig. 1). Schools for children with special needs and those with fewer than 50 students (with on average of 22 students each) were excluded from the analysis. These schools often face distinct logistical and accessibility challenges and serve specific needs that are not directly comparable to those of the broader school population included in this study. While excluded from this analysis, their unique needs are equally important and would benefit from more targeted assessments. The available dataset from 2019 (Stockholms stad, 2019) was updated to reflect schools that had closed, merged, or changed location. The catchment area of each school was defined using

Fig. 1. Focus schools within Stockholm, along with their generated catchment buffer areas. (Data source: Stockholms stad (2019). Stockholms stad. (2019). *Grundskolor och gymnasieskolor*. <https://www.openstreetmap.org/#map=2/54.2/-52.4>.

a 2 km service network area, restricted to municipal boundaries. This method ensured accessibility within a reasonable distance. The 2 km threshold was identified as a division line between the use of motorised and non-motorised transport modes for school journeys (Kelly and Fu, 2014), and 90 % of pupils in grades 0–3 and 80 % of pupils in grades 4–6 in Stockholm lived within this distance of their school (Stockholms stad, 2016). Given Stockholm’s high population and school density, nearly all city streets function as school routes. While Euclidean distance is a commonly used measure, it may not accurately reflect actual travel distances (Liu et al., 2020). The road network, instead of the cycling network, was used to calculate the buffer zone, reflecting the potential area served if cycling network existed.

2.2. Selection of school bikeability indicators

The study builds on the literature review and the resulting list of indicators for children’s school bikeability of Paulusová & Sharmeen (Paulusová and Sharmeen, 2024). The indicators, categorised into cycling infrastructure, connectivity and urbanization, safety, and surrounding environment, are summarised in Table 1.

The indicators were refined to include only built environment characteristics, excluding traffic volumes, collisions, criminality, and air quality. Due to data unavailability, certain indicators—such as lighting, cycle path width, pavement quality, obstacles, aesthetics, and signage indicating navigability through the environment—had to be omitted. While winter maintenance is crucial in Northern countries (Suomalainen et al., 2024), the lack of relevant data (such as winter

maintenance or a width of cycle path enabling winter maintenance) means that the index used here may be more suitable for non-winter seasons. The influence of land use mix on children’s cycling accessibility is understudied and inconsistent. Much of the existing literature focuses on active school travel or children’s independent mobility, rather than cycling specifically. Findings across studies are mixed. For instance, a meta-analysis by Sharmin and Kamruzzaman (2017) including three studies examining land use mix found a generally negative but highly inconsistent association between land-use mix and children’s independent travel, though a positive association was observed for the proportion of residential and commercial land uses. Yarlagadda and Srinivasan (2007) reported that land-use mix was not a significant predictor of children’s mode choice to school. Similarly, Carver et al. (2014) found no significant relationship between land-use mix (defined as the colocation of residences, businesses, and sports facilities) and walking or cycling to school in a cross-sectional analysis; however, they did observe a positive association for girls in a longitudinal analysis. On the other hand, Larsen et al. (2009) and De Meester et al. (2014) both identified a positive association between land-use mix and children’s active travel. Given these mixed findings, land-use mix was excluded from this analysis. Similarly, destinations—though important for cycling accessibility (Wangzom et al., 2023)—were excluded since primary schools themselves are the focal destinations. Despite these exclusions, the final set of indicators captured the most significant built environment factors affecting school cycling with a strong emphasis on traffic safety and cycling connectivity (Broberg and Sarjala, 2015; Huertas-Delgado et al., 2017; Ikeda et al., 2020; Scheiner et al., 2019).

Table 1
Indicators for a school bikeability index from Paulusová and Sharmeen (2024), with marked indicators excluded in this study. (BE = built environment).

Category	Indicator	Inclusion in the index
Cycling infrastructure	Presence of bicycle infrastructure	Included.
	Type of bicycle infrastructure	Included.
	Width of bicycle paths	Excluded, missing data.
	Pavement type and quality	Excluded, missing data.
	Quality of bicycle infrastructure at intersections	Included.
	Signage/ signalling	Excluded, missing data.
	Bicycle parking	Included.
	Obstacles on bicycle paths	Excluded, missing data.
Connectivity and urbanization	Street connectivity/ Intersection density	Included.
	Degree of urbanization	Included.
Safety	Traffic control devices and speed limiting measures	Included.
	Bicycle traffic volume	Excluded, not a BE factor.
	Traffic volume	Excluded, not a BE factor.
	Lightning	Excluded, missing data.
	Traffic speed	Included.
	Road type	Included.
	Collisions	Excluded, not a BE factor.
	School site entrance and location	Included.
	Criminality	Excluded, not a BE factor.
	Pedestrian traffic flow	Excluded, not a BE factor.
Surrounding environment	Slope	Included.
	Aesthetics and attractiveness	Excluded, missing data.
	Air quality	Excluded, not a BE factor.

2.3. Refinement of indicators based on local context

To incorporate local characteristics, some of the indicators (especially related to cycling infrastructure, connectivity and traffic safety) were further refined, primarily based on the Plan (Stockholms stad, 2016). The Plan, incorporated into the city’s accessibility strategy and urban mobility plan (Stockholms stad, 2022a), aims to enhance school route safety and accessibility while promoting active mobility. Though not legally binding, these documents reflect local expertise and the city’s traffic administration efforts. The Plan sets three overarching goals: creating safe and secure routes to school, promoting new travel habits to increase the number of pedestrians and cyclists, and developing a comprehensive city-wide approach to address school routes.

The Plan defines several factors that are important for increased safety of children when travelling to schools, including the school location, safe and connected cycle paths, lightning, signage, and winter maintenance. It further mentions that it is preferred for safety reasons when the schools entrance is located on local streets rather than main streets, and especially that the school entrance should be connected with a safe cycling path. According to the Plan, a cycle path is considered safe for children if it runs along a street where the speed does not exceed 30 km/h. At higher speeds, there should be a cycle lane or a physically separated cycle lane in some other way. It is important to clarify the terms used in the study, as they are in contrast from the Plan. In this study, "cycle lane" refers to a painted lane for bicycles that is not physically separated from motorised vehicle lanes, while "cycle path" refers to a dedicated path that is physically or grade-separated from traffic. Further, the Plan states that schools should not be located in industrial environments. This could have occurred in the past due to the rapid development of some urban areas and the need for new schools. Signage around school should be used to alert car drivers about the presence of a school nearby, and cycle paths should also be easily navigable.

There may be additional factors that would be relevant in certain contexts but are not relevant in Sweden. For example, the presence of sidewalks might be important for cycling accessibility in the North American context (Mitra, 2013). However, in Sweden, children above the age of 8 are not allowed to cycle on sidewalks (Nationella

trafiksäkerhetsförbundet), and such indicator is, therefore, excluded from the index.

3. Methods

3.1. SBI

The index in this study comprised of 14 indicators, two of which have two sub-indicators. Table 2 summarizes the indicators and their definitions. The final SBI was the sum of individual indicators, multiplied by its weights (Equation 1). The weights account for the varying impact of each indicator on the likelihood of cycling to school, similarly to the approach used in Rugtvedt (2019). The calculation of indicators and the method for determining weights are explained in the next sections.

3.1.1. Indicators data

The values for each indicator were calculated using publicly available data, supplemented by Google Street View and satellite images when necessary (see Table 2 for more details).

There are two main datasets regarding the cycling network and infrastructure in Stockholm: Cykelstråk (Fig. 2; Stockholms stad 2023a) and GCM_vägtyp (Fig. 3; Stockholms stad (2023e)). The former represents the designated cycling network, which is independent of the type of bicycle infrastructure provided. In contrast, the latter contains data on the bicycle infrastructure itself. A limitation of the latter dataset is its incompleteness. Although it was continuously updated until 2023, some discrepancies with reality were noted, and the extent of its incompleteness was difficult to assess. Both datasets were used to compute different indicators based on specific requirements. For example, a significant part of the cycling infrastructure (GCM_vägtyp, Fig. 3) consists of shared walking and cycling paths, which are largely excluded from the main and primary cycling networks (Cykelstråk, Fig. 2). While such shared paths may not be preferred by commuters due to slower riding speeds, they can be suitable for children precisely because of their lower speeds and more local usage. Cykelstråk dataset was therefore used for examining the presence of any cycling infrastructure, and GCM_vägtyp for examining separated and children-friendly cycling infrastructure.

3.1.2. Indicators calculation

All indicators were computed using the open-source software QGIS. Most indicators were quantified and normalised on a scale from 0 to 1, while four indicators were binary, based on the presence or absence of certain features (with one indicator allowing a value of 0.5; see Table 2). Using normalised values instead of assigning scores (such as creating score classes with equal distribution or fixed intervals) minimises researcher subjectivity in the scoring process. This is beneficial, as there is no established value for most of the indicators. Therefore, the index was relative, comparing school areas to one another rather than establishing absolute best or worst values. This approach enabled effective comparability between different school catchment areas.

To compute the density of intersections with bicycle infrastructure, a data layer of road intersections (excluding roads within parking areas and roads where cyclists are prohibited) was intersected with a data layer on bicycle crossings and passages. The average degree of urbanization was calculated using a 1 km x 1 km population density grid. A layer of random points was generated, where the number of points in each grid cell was equal to the total number of residents in that cell. The total number of random points within each school catchment area was summed and scaled by area to determine the average degree of urbanization.

The preferred road type indicator was based on the road traffic network classification, which ranks roads from 0 (most important roads) to 9 (least important) for connectivity in the network (Trafikverket, 2020). Road classes preferred for cycling included classes 7, 8, and 9, which include smaller local streets and roads within residential, park and industrial areas. Roads classified as 6 or lower were not considered

Table 2
Refined school bikeability index.

Indicator	Variable	Output value	Data (source)
Cycling infrastructure			
1. Cycling network	Length of bicycle network, compared to the total length of the road network within the buffer zone.	Ratio, normalised.	Cykelstråk (Stockholms stad, 2023a), Vägtrafiknät (Trafikverket, 2023b)
2. Recommended cycling infrastructure for children	Length of bike lanes along roads with a maximum speed limit of 30 km/h and physically separated bicycle paths within the buffer zone, compared to the length of the road network.	Ratio, normalised.	GCM-vägtyp (Stockholms stad, 2023e), Vägtrafiknät (Trafikverket, 2023)
3. Physically separated infrastructure	Length of physically separated bicycle paths (both shared with pedestrians and exclusive for cyclists) within the buffer zone, compared to the length of the road network.	Ratio, normalised.	GCM-vägtyp (Stockholms stad, 2023e), Vägtrafiknät (Trafikverket, 2023)
4. Intersections with bicycle infrastructure	Number of road intersections with dedicated bicycle infrastructure (e.g. bicycle passage or crossing) within the buffer zone, compared to the total number of road intersections. Data on other types of bicycle infrastructure (bicycle boxes, traffic lights etc.) were not available.	Ratio, normalised.	GCM-vägtyp (Stockholms stad, 2023e), Gatutyp (Stockholms stad, 2023d), Bro och Tunnel (Stockholms stad, 2023b)
5. Connectivity of school with cycling infrastructure	Presence of a bicycle path or lane close to school entrance.	0 if poorly connected ^a . 0.5 if some connections exist ^b . 1 if well connected ^c .	Manual observation, Cykelstråk (Stockholms stad, 2023a), GCM-vägtyp (Stockholms stad, 2023e)
6. Bicycle parking at school	Presence of bicycle parking at school (type not distinguished).	0 if not present. 1 if present.	Manual observation. Existing data on Open Street Map or Stockholm Open Data portal are insufficient.
Connectivity and urbanization			
7. Intersection density	Number of intersections within the buffer zone, compared to the total area of the buffer zone.	Density, normalised.	Gatutyp (Stockholms stad, 2023d), Bro och Tunnel (Stockholms stad, 2023b)
8. Degree of urbanization	Number of residents within the buffer zone, compared to the total area of the buffer zone.	Density, normalised.	Total Population (SCB, 2022)
Safety			

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Indicator	Variable	Output value	Data (source)
9. Speed limit at school entrance	30 km/h speed limit at school entrance (within 100 m by road from the school).	0 if above 30 km/h. 1 if 30 km/h and lower.	Hastingsgräns (Stockholms stad, 2023 f)
10. Average maximum traffic speed limit	Average maximum speed limit of roads within the school buffer zone. Roads with walking speed limit were assigned speed of 7 km/h.	Value normalised and inverted for negative effect.	Hastingsgräns (Stockholms stad, 2023 f)
11. Speed limiting measures	Density of speedbumps within the buffer zone, compared to the total area of the buffer zone. Presence of signage announcing school zone.	Density, normalised. 0 if not present. 1 if present.	Farthinder (Stockholms stad, 2023c) Manual inspection via Google Streetview
12. Preferred Road type	Length of roads of preferred functional class within the buffer zone, compared to the total length of the road network.	Ratio, normalised.	Funktionell vägklass (Trafikverket, 2020)
Environment			
13. Slope	Slope of school access roads (average slope within 100 m service area). Average slope of roads within the school buffer area.	Slope in degrees. Value normalised and inverted for negative effect.	Slope (Copernicus, 2023) Slope (Copernicus, 2023)
14. Nature	Density of green areas within the school buffer zone.	Density, normalised.	Open Street Map (OpenStreetMap, 2015)

(1)

$$\begin{aligned}
 SBI_i = & w_1 * BikeInfrastructure_{norm,i} \\
 + & w_2 * ChildInfrastructure_{norm,i} \\
 + & w_3 * SeparatedInfrastructure_{norm,i} \\
 + & w_4 * IntersectionsInfrastructure_{norm,i} \\
 + & w_5 * EntranceConnectivity_{norm,i} \\
 + & w_6 * BikeParking_{norm,i} \\
 + & w_7 * IntersectionsDensity_{norm,i} \\
 + & w_8 * DegreeUrbanization_{norm,i} \\
 + & w_9 * EntranceSpeed_{norm,i} \\
 + & w_{10} * (1 - AverageSpeed_{norm,i}) \\
 + & w_{11} * (0.5 * Speedbumps_{norm,i} + 0.5 * SchoolSignage_{norm,i}) \\
 + & w_{12} * ResidentialRoadType_{norm,i} \\
 + & w_{13} * (0.5 * (1 - EntranceSlope_{norm,i}) + 0.5 * (1 - AverageSlope_{norm,i})) \\
 + & w_{14} * GreenSpace_{norm,i}
 \end{aligned}$$

^a Poorly connected means that the main school access road has no recommended bicycle infrastructure for children, and has a bikeable connection from fewer than two other directions besides the main access road.

^b Some connection means that the main access road has bicycle infrastructure recommended for children, or that the school can be accessed by bicycle infrastructure from at least two other directions.

^c Well connected means that the main access road has bicycle infrastructure recommended for children and that the school can be accessed by bicycle infrastructure from another direction

preferable, as they are larger streets collecting traffic from central, residential or industrial parts of the city and form part of the main public transport line network. While streets with lower classifications may not permit cycling, their presence may influence perceptions of traffic safety in the area (Giles-Corti et al., 2011), and they were therefore included in

the computation of certain indicators.

3.1.3. Weighting methodology

The weights reflect guardians' perceptions, as discussed in Sections 1 and 2.1, because guardians' perceptions are more influential than those of children when deciding the mode of transport to school, particularly for primary school children. This approach has been commonly used in similar studies (e.g., Zhu et al., 2024). These weights were obtained through an online, self-reported survey aimed at guardians of children in grades 1–6 in Stockholm for the 2022/2023 school year. If guardians had multiple children in grades 1–6, they were asked to consider their youngest child when responding. Due to data privacy and research ethics guidelines that limit access to contact details for children and guardians, the survey was distributed through school administrations (across all 222 schools) and parents' associations, wherever possible. It was also shared with the Transport Advisory Services department at WSP Sverige in Stockholm. The survey did not require additional ethical approval beyond the general legal framework for academic research and GDPR guidelines in Sweden, as it collected only anonymized responses provided by guardians/adults. Responses were collected between 15/05/2023 and 03/06/2023.

The survey used a Likert-type scale to assess how respondents valued various factors, in their decision to allow their children to cycle to school. Possible responses ranged from 1 (Not at all important) to 5 (Very much important). To aid accurate understanding, some questions were accompanied by photos depicting relevant street conditions from Stockholm (Appendix 1). In addition to these ratings, the survey collected socio-demographic information (guardian's and child's gender, the school grade the child attended, and number of children in household) and data on school travel behaviour (distance to school, frequency of cycling to school, including alone, with others, or a cargo bike, and the main travel mode). The survey concluded with three open-ended questions asking about other factors that may influence cycling, whether the season affects cycling and how, and any additional comments.

The indicator weights were calculated as the mean values of the Likert-scale responses, using SPSS software. To investigate whether these weights varied across different respondent groups, further analysis was conducted based on prior literature suggesting e.g., differences between cyclists and non-cyclists (Motta, 2017). Bivariate statistical tests, performed in R, included t-tests applied to dichotomous variables (e.g., guardian gender), and one-way ANOVA with post-hoc Tukey comparisons used for variables with three groups (e.g., travel mode). These analyses examined whether the perceived importance of the indicators differed significantly by guardians' and children's characteristics, such as gender, school grade, and travel mode to school.

3.2. Comparative analyses

To gain a deeper understanding of the differences in school bikeability, further assessment was conducted focusing on selected schools and school pairs. Firstly, schools with the highest and lowest bikeability scores were compared to examine what factors are most hindering bikeability and where schools with high bikeability scores still have potential for improvement.

Secondly, three neighbouring school pairs with different SBI scores were selected for in-depth analysis. Due to the nature of the index (focused on built environment features), schools located close to each other were likely to score similarly. Relatively small differences were expected in neighbouring schools that share a significant part of their surroundings. Thus, a closer assessment of such pairs could provide insights into the causal factors for these differences. Further assessments were conducted through a closer examination of the indicator values and in-person site visits. Site visits were carried out to evaluate the surrounding areas and assess how well the reality aligns with the data and insights provided by the index. These visits took place during school

Fig. 2. Fig. 1. Cycling network. Dataset Cykelstråk (Stockholms stad, 2023a). Stockholms stad. (2023a). *Cykelstråk*. <https://dataportalen.stockholm.se/dataportalen/GetMetaDataById?id=LvFeature20022411&showmetadatiview>.

holidays, between June 26th and 28th, 2023.

3.3. Income inequality analysis

Although income does not directly affect bikeability and was therefore not included in the SBI, previous research has identified a positive correlation between the presence of cycling infrastructure and average income levels in an area (Flanagan et al., 2016). To examine possible equity aspects related to bikeability, the SBI scores were compared with income, a key socio-economic indicator. This relationship was examined using a simple regression analysis in R across Stockholm's 132 administrative areas. The income data were obtained from the city's official statistics for each of these areas (Stockholms stad, 2024a) and reflect the average yearly income of individuals aged 16 and above in 2021. Administrative areas with missing income data (due to low population levels) or without any schools were excluded from the analysis. The SBI scores were averaged over the schools located within each administrative areas.

4. Results

4.1. Indicators

Table 3 presents descriptive statistics for all indicators included in the index. The values represent conditions within each school's catchment area. The table reveals considerable variability across several indicators. For example, the proportion of any cycling infrastructure ranges from as low as 3.3 % to over 60 % of the total road length, with a mean of 31.0 % (SD = 11.3 %). Similarly, physically separated infrastructure and recommended child-friendly cycling infrastructure also show substantial variation, suggesting unequal access to safe infrastructure across school catchment areas. In some areas, the ratio of

child-friendly and separated cycling infrastructure even exceeds 1, therefore there is more cycling paths compared to roads (in length). Some indicators, such as bicycle parking at schools and school connectivity with cycling paths, are binary or categorical, reflecting whether such infrastructure is present or not. For these, the mean values (e.g., 0.694 for bicycle parking) give an indication of prevalence across the city's schools.

4.2. Weights

The survey received responses from 94 children's guardians. Due to the way the survey was distributed (Section 3.1), the response rate was unknown. The descriptive statistics of the respondents are presented in Table 4, in comparison with national or local statistics, where available. The responses were skewed towards female respondents and potentially younger children. According to the survey, the majority of the children (70 %) travelled less than 2 km to school, suggesting that the definition of the school catchment area for this study is reasonable. Most children usually walked to school (43 %), and 23 % of children cycled to school (either alone or with others such as parents, siblings or friends). Less than half (40 %) of respondents indicated that their child never cycled to school. The mean weights for each indicator, as presented in Table 5, revealed that the highest weights were assigned to the presence of bicycle parking, followed by the speed limit at the school entrance. The lowest mean weights were assigned to the presence of physically separated cycling infrastructure and cycling infrastructure at intersections.

The bivariate statistical analysis examined the association between respondents' evaluations of the importance of various indicators (measured on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 to 5) and their own as well as their children's characteristics. Several statistically significant differences emerged (Table 6). The most notable differences in the perceived importance of indicators were observed between male and female

Fig. 3. Cycling infrastructure network. Dataset GCM-vägtyp (Stockholms stad, 2023b).

Stockholms stad. (2023b). NVDB - GCM-vägtyp. <https://dataportalen.stockholm.se/dataportalen/GetMetaDataById?id=LvFeature4000099&showmetadaview>.

guardians, with women assigning significantly greater importance to the presence of cycling infrastructure (in general, suitable for children, at intersections and at school entrances), as well as to the availability of bicycle parking. The difference in scores regarding the connection of school entrance with bicycle infrastructure was the largest observed. In contrast, the gender of the child showed minimal influences on responses, with the exception of the slope indicator. Guardians of female children assigned higher importance to slope. Among travel mode groups, guardians whose child was usually driven to school by car rated the slope of the route as more important than those whose children walked or cycled. Additionally, guardians of younger children (grades 1–3) placed significantly higher importance on the presence of separated and child-friendly cycling infrastructure, the connectivity of the school with a cycle path, and intersection density, compared to guardians of older children (grades 4–6). Conversely, guardians of older children assigned greater importance to slope, compared to those of younger children.

In the open questions, several factors emerged that may influence the decision to allow children to cycle to school, especially in winter. Concerns included slippery roads, insufficient snow removal, and darkness. The most frequently mentioned factors were: too many unsupervised (and dangerous) crossings and intersections (mentioned by 10 respondents), heavy car traffic (7) and manoeuvring drivers (5) around the school, discontinuous cycle paths (5), reckless cyclists (5), lack of cycling culture within the family (4), long distance to school (9), and weather conditions (5).

4.3. SBI results

The SBI was computed using both unweighted and weighted scores. The unweighted scores ranged from 3.2 to 7.8, with a mean score value of 5.8 (SD = 0.89), from the possible range of 0–14 (Fig. 4). The

weighted SBI scores ranged from 11 to 26.3, with a mean score value of 19.1 (SD = 3.1), from a possible range of 0–46 (Fig. 5). When comparing the maps illustrating the weighted and unweighted SBI scores, there did not appear to be large differences in the final SBI scores (weighted vs. unweighted) each school received. However, clusters of schools with higher, average, or lower scores indicated potentially problematic areas for cycling.

Schools in proximity tended to have similar SBI scores, as was expected due to the nature of the index and its indicators. Some exceptions existed, which are discussed in detail in Section 4.3.2. Schools located in the southwest and mid-northwest of the municipality generally had lower scores. In contrast, schools located in the north and in the centre of the municipality received higher scores on average. Schools in the western and southern part of the municipality received relatively average scores. These insights highlight some spatial infrastructural disparities where improvements might be necessary. Schools in the city centre had above-average values for indicators such as the presence of any cycling infrastructure, intersections with bicycle infrastructure, degree of urbanization, and maximum average speed limit. However, these schools scored low on recommended cycling infrastructure for children and separated cycling infrastructure. In contrast, schools in the north of the municipality received high values for these two indicators; discussed further in Section 4.3.1. Additionally, city centre schools had lower-than-average values for school connectivity with bicycle infrastructure, nature, and road type indicators. Schools in the north and southwest were characterised by low values for intersections with cycling infrastructure, degree of urbanization, any cycling infrastructure and speed bumps. Interestingly, speed limit at school entrance and school zone signage did not exhibit any notable pattern across Stockholm.

Table 3

Descriptive statistics for the indicator values included in the SBI for Stockholm. All presented values are for the school catchment area and are before normalisation.

Indicator	Min	Max	Mean (SD)	Mean after normalisation (SD)
1. Any cycling infrastructure (% of total road length)	0.033	0.608	0.310 (0.113)	0.482 (0.198)
2. Recommended cycling infrastructure for children (% of total road length)	0.212	1.169	0.447 (0.178)	0.246 (0.187)
3. Physically separated infrastructure (% of total road length)	0.212	1.169	0.433 (0.184)	0.231 (0.192)
4. Intersections with bicycle infrastructure (% of total intersections)	0	0.307	0.123 (0.080)	0.399 (0.259)
5. Connectivity of school with cycle path	0	1	0.367 (0.341)	-
6. Bicycle parking at school	0	1	0.694 (0.462)	-
7. Intersection density (per km ²)	25.417	151.855	82.024 (21.754)	0.448 (0.172)
8. Degree of urbanization (population per km ²)	256.019	17656.6	6912.550 (3691.540)	0.383 (0.212)
9. Speed limit at school entrance	0	1	0.473 (0.500)	-
10. Average maximum speed limit (in km/h)	30.681	49.378	38.441 (3.969)	0.415 (0.212)
11. Speed limiting measures				
a) speed bumps (per km ²)	1.726	34.801	11.884 (7.157)	0.307 (0.216)
b) signage announcing school zone	0	1	0.532 (0.500)	-
12. Road type preference (% of residential roads to all roads)	0.475	0.924	0.659 (0.096)	0.410 (0.215)
13. Slope				
a) at the entrance roads	0	3.896	0.408 (0.633)	0.105 (0.162)
b) average within the school buffer area	0.026	3.503	0.703 (0.607)	0.195 (0.174)
14. Nature (% of green space to total area)	5.825	63.808	24.947 (9.571)	0.330 (0.165)

4.3.1. Comparative analysis 1 - schools with highest and lowest SBI scores

To compare the state of the lowest and highest scoring schools and explore potential development opportunities for these schools, three of the highest and lowest scoring schools were selected (Fig. 6). These schools were chosen to represent different areas, as schools located close to each other tend to have similar scores. The values for the individual indicators are presented in Fig. 7. Neither the highest scoring schools achieved high scores across all the indicators, nor did the lowest scoring schools scored consistently low. The prevalence of high scores among well-performing schools was evident for certain indicators, such as those related to cycling infrastructure, including the connectivity of the school with bicycle infrastructure, bicycle parking, degree of urbanization, and speed bumps.

Low-scoring schools received a score of zero on a few indicators. The low values of these schools were further amplified by the weights in the final scores, with some of their poorest indicators receiving the highest weights. Many of the indicators on which low-scoring schools received low scores offer relatively good potential for improvement. For example, building bicycle parking, connecting the school entrance with bicycle

Table 4

Descriptive statistics of the survey respondents, compared to national statistics.

Descriptive statistics for demographic characteristics of respondents	National or local statistics
Gender of respondent	
Women	74.5 %
Men	25.5 %
Number of children	
1	18.1 %
2	64.9 %
3	13.8 %
More than 3	3.2 %
Gender of child	
Women	43.6 %
Men	52.1 %
Prefer not to respond	4.3 %
Main transport mode to school	
Cycling	24.5 %
Walking	44.7 %
Public transit	21.3 %
Car	9.6 %
Cycling frequency to school	
Always (5 days a week)	17 %
Often (3–5 days a week)	8.5 %
Occasionally (1–2 days a week)	19.2 %
Less than once a week	17 %
Never	38.3 %
Grade the child attended in academic year 2022/2023	
1	25.5 %
2	18.1 %
3	11.7 %
4	12.8 %
5	16.0 %
6	16.0 %

^a The population of Sweden in 2022 (SCB, 2022).

^b The data are based on the number of siblings living at home among children and young persons aged 0–21 in Sweden (SCB, 2022).

^c The data are based on the Swedish population by age in 2021, accounting for children between the ages 5–14, thus covering a larger age range than this study (SCB, 2022).

^d The data are from a study (Björklid and Gummesson, 2013) examining school travel in five Swedish schools (four of which are located in the greater Stockholm area). Data differ based on whether the respondent was the child's guardian (G) or the child themselves (C).

Table 5

Weight distribution based on responses from the survey.

Indicator	Mean weight	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness
1. Any cycling infrastructure	3.45	1.22	- 0.81	- 0.41
2. Recommended cycling infrastructure for children	2.82	1.41	- 1.25	0.14
3. Physically separated infrastructure	2.64	1.56	- 1.50	0.28
4. Intersections with bicycle infrastructure	2.59	1.47	- 1.22	0.40
5. Connectivity of school with cycle path	2.67	1.46	- 1.25	0.38
6. Bicycle parking at school.	4.24	0.92	- 0.24	- 0.93
7. Intersection density	3.37	1.18	- 0.47	- 0.41
8. Degree of urbanization	4.01	1.06	0.04	- 0.90
9. Speed limit at school entrance	3.93	1.26	- 0.28	- 0.89
10. Average maximum speed limit	3.52	1.07	- 0.57	- 0.14
11. Speed limiting measures (presence of speed bumps and signage announcing the school zone)	3.04	1.27	- 0.94	- 0.15
12. Road type	3.48	1.23	- 0.76	- 0.38
13. Slope (at the entrance roads and average within the school buffer area)	2.83	1.27	- 0.93	0.10
14. Nature space	3.30	1.26	- 0.82	- 0.35

Table 6

Results of bivariate analysis showing differences in indicator scores based on respondents' survey responses and their own and their children's characteristics. The table presents only statistically significant differences ($p < 0.1$) identified through t-tests and ANOVA.

Indicator	Variable	Comparison (Group 1 – Group 2) ^a	Mean ^b (Gr. 1)	Mean ^b (Gr. 2)	Mean diff.	p-value	95 % CI
Any cycling infrastructure	Guardian gender	Female – Male	3.61	2.96	+ 0.65	0.023	[0.10, 1.22]
Recommended cycling infrastructure for children	Guardian gender	Female – Male	3.00	2.29	+ 0.71	0.024	[0.10, 1.32]
	Grade	Low – High	3.06	2.52	+ 0.54	0.066	[-0.04, 1.10]
Physically separated infrastructure	Grade	Low – High	2.90	2.31	+ 0.59	0.061	[-0.03, 1.22]
Intersections with bicycle infrastructure	Guardian gender	Female – Male	2.74	2.12	+ 0.62	0.040	[0.03, 1.21]
Connectivity of school with cycle path	Guardian gender	Female – Male	2.89	2.04	+ 0.85	0.005	[0.27, 1.42]
	Grade	Low – High	2.94	2.33	+ 0.61	0.040	[0.03, 1.19]
Bicycle parking	Guardian gender	Female – Male	4.39	3.83	+ 0.56	0.026	[0.07, 1.03]
Intersection density	Grade	Low – High	3.65	3.02	+ 0.63	0.011	[0.15, 1.11]
	Child gender	Female – Male	3.22	2.57	+ 0.65	0.038	[0.03, 1.27]
Slope	Grade	Low – High	2.56	3.17	-0.61	0.019	[-1.12, -0.10]
	Main transport mode to school	Car – Walking	4.01	3.23	+ 0.78	0.024	[0.12, 2.61]
		Car – Cycling	4.01	3.65	+ 0.36	0.064	[-0.05, 2.61]

^a Low grade included children in grades 1–3. High grade included children in grades 4–6.

^b Mean values refer to the average scores assigned to each indicator by different respondent groups. The unit of measurement is a 5-point Likert scale (ranging from 1 to 5).

Fig. 4. Unweighted SBI scores.

infrastructure, installing more speed bumps in the school area, or adding school zone signs are relatively straightforward changes. These improvements are generally more feasible than, for instance, increasing the degree of urbanization. It is also evident that schools generally perform poorly in terms of having separated and child-friendly bicycle infrastructure. Interestingly, there were indicators, such as nature and road type, where the lowest-scoring schools scored better than the highest-

scoring schools, suggesting potential for improvement in the currently highest-scoring schools. While some indicators, such as slope, may represent significant challenges for improvement, adjustments to road categories or increasing green areas could enhance bikeability.

Fig. 5. Weighted SBI scores.

4.3.2. Comparative analysis 2 – Schools in proximity with varying SBI scores

Three pairs of schools were selected for further in-depth analysis due to their significantly different scores while being located in close proximity (Fig. 8). These pairs were situated in various parts of the municipality, each characterised by different factors. Key differences between the school pairs included the connectivity of school entrance with bicycle paths, the presence of bike parking, the maximum speed at the school entrance, and school zone signage. For Cordoba International School and Oxhagskolan, additional differences included the presence of separated bicycle infrastructure, average maximum speed, and bicycle infrastructure suitable for children.

The site visit revealed few noteworthy observations. Firstly, some school access roads (e.g., Sofia skola, Hjortagens skola), despite having a speed limit of 30 km/h, were part of the main public transit network. This contradicted the recommendations in the Plan (Stockholms stad, 2016), suggesting unsuitability of these routes for children cycling. Further, some inconsistencies in the speed limit data were found, which could explain the deviations in SBI scores. For instance, in the case of Hjortagens skola, the road network service area of 100 m used to compute the indicator for maximum speed near the school entrance included a side access road with a speed limit of 50 km/h (Fig. 9). As it was unlikely that the road would actually be driven at 50 km/h, the school could have scored higher on this indicator, potentially improving its overall score by 3.93 points. Sofia skola was accessible via a shared walking and pedestrian path from the southeast (Fig. 10), which contributed to a partial score on the school-bike connectivity indicator. However, it was unclear how many children accessed the school from the south, where bicycle access was available, versus those who come from the north, where there was no suitable bicycle access, although it was a more residential area.

In the case of Oxhagskolan and Cordoba International School, there

was a noticeable difference in the separation of transport modes, which also extended to the availability of separated bicycle infrastructure. This significant separation may have explained the lack of school zone signs, speed bumps, and the high average speeds in the area. With effective separation of motorised and non-motorised vehicles, these indicators may become less relevant. In such situations, it would be advisable to account for the interactions between indicators. Oxhagskolan could have potentially achieved a higher score if some of these interactions had been considered. Furthermore, the indicator of connectivity, which was calculated based on road intersection density, may have been less relevant in areas with high separation of transport modes and thus separate networks.

4.3.3. Income inequality analysis

The distributions of average income and SBI scores are illustrated in Fig. 11. The analysis showed no significant relationship between the average income in city's administrative areas and the average SBI score for schools in the same area (coefficient = 1.80×10^{-6} , p-value = 0.32). This suggests that bikeability was not subject to income inequality, and that schools in both wealthier and poorer areas could exhibit good bikeability, and vice versa.

5. Discussion and conclusion

The study assessed the bikeability of primary schools in Stockholm, aiming to answer how accessible these schools are by bicycle for their pupils. It operationalised built environment indicators of school bikeability to compute the School Bikeability Index for Stockholm.

According to the survey results, the most important factors influencing children's bikeability were the availability of bicycle parking at school, the degree of urbanization, and the speed limit at the school entrance. Conversely, the least important factors were physically

Fig. 6. Selected lowest- and highest-scoring schools. As all schools satisfying the conditions explained in 2.1 were included in the analysis, some schools with specific target groups, such as Lycée Français Saint Louis (an international school), were also subject to the analysis. Such schools may have a larger catchment area. The bikeability score for this school (and similar ones) may therefore not be fully relevant as the number of students living in cycling distance to the school is expected to be lower. The final bikeability score for such schools is thus rather illustrative.

Fig. 7. Weighted scores for all indicators for the selected schools. Lowest-scoring schools are in red, highest-scoring schools are in blue.

Fig. 8. Schools selected for further analysis, including Hjorthagens skola (with a final weighted score of 12.8) and Bobergsskolan (20.5), Montessoriskola Anne Frank (17.1) and Sofia skola (24.1), and Cordoba International School (13.8) and Oxhagsskolan (24.2).

separated bicycle infrastructure, bicycle infrastructure connected to the school entrance, and intersections with bicycle infrastructure. This finding was somewhat surprising and counterintuitive. However, previous studies, though not specifically focused on children, have also found relatively lower weights to cycling infrastructure compared to other factors (e.g., Arellana et al., 2020). Additionally, research on school travel mode choice has found that traffic safety and bicycle tracks may have an insignificant impact (e.g., de Vries et al., 2010; Helbich, 2016). A Swedish study by Westman et al. (2017) looking at the determinants of car use to school found that safety and security concerns became insignificant after controlling for other factors, suggesting that worries about safety and security do not directly drive higher car use or lower levels of active travel. The study concluded that this finding might have occurred due to the fact that it focused on children aged 10–15 years old, who in Sweden tend to become autonomous at an earlier age than their peers in many other countries. Another possible explanation for the lower importance of cycling infrastructure could be specific local conditions. Guardians may have perceived cycling in Stockholm as relatively safe, or they may have not viewed cycling paths as a key determinant due to their heavy use during rush hours, which could have made them feel less suitable for children.

Variations in preferences also emerged based on guardians' characteristics. Notably, female guardians assigned greater importance to bicycle infrastructure compared to male guardians, guardians of younger children placed greater emphasis on safety-related aspects such as school connectivity via cycle paths and speed limits at school entrances, and guardians whose children primarily traveled to school by car attributed higher importance to slope. These results seem to align with existing empirical evidence: women are usually more concerned about cycling safety (Aldred et al., 2017); parents of younger children tend to report more barriers than parents of older children or adolescents

(Aranda-Balboa et al., 2020); and steeper slopes are a known deterrent for non-cyclists (Motta, 2017).

The findings from spatial analysis revealed that the bikeability of different school areas largely depended on a few indicators: the presence of bicycle parking, connectivity through bicycle infrastructure, maximum speed limits near schools, and the presence of school zone signs. A major shortcoming identified across these school areas was the lack of cycling infrastructure suitable for children, particularly in terms of design and speed limits on adjacent roads. Even some schools located in close proximity to one another, with shared catchment zones and expected to score similarly, exhibited varying final scores due to these indicators.

The analysis of school bikeability and income suggested no significant relationship. A previous study (Ljungemyr, 2022) that examined the relationship between income and the presence of cycling infrastructure across 13 local government areas in the Stockholm municipality found a negative correlation, indicating that low-income areas had better access to cycling infrastructure. While this finding contrasted with previous research, which usually highlighted a positive relationship, the negative or insignificant relationships observed in Stockholm suggest that low-income areas are not disadvantaged in terms of school bikeability.

5.1. Strengths

A key strength of this study is its focus on a specific user group within the field of bikeability research. Unlike previous bikeability indices, this study specifically focused on the needs of children, which differ from those of adult cyclists (Mitra, 2013), presenting an important step toward promoting active travel among school children. The inclusion of guardian-informed indicator weights added contextual sensitivity to the

Fig. 9. Maximum speed limits on roads close to Hjorthagens skola.

Fig. 10. Bicycle infrastructure network nearby Montessori Anne Frank and Sofia skola.

analysis, ensuring that the index reflected real-world preferences and concerns rather than relying solely on expert judgment or theoretical frameworks.

Another strength of the research is its relevance to policy makers. The insights from the research could help city planners enhance school

bikeability through potentially less resource-intensive measures. By providing a clear and data-driven assessment of bikeability, the index could inform targeted interventions and resource allocation. For instance, it could assist in prioritizing investments in cycling infrastructure in areas of greatest need, thereby maximizing the impact of

Fig. 11. Map of SBI scores and average yearly income in thousands of Swedish kronas.

limited resources (Pucher et al., 2010).

By undertaking a closer examination of particular areas (in terms of data and in-person surveys), the study also uncovered some inconsistencies in the existing open-source data, particularly regarding infrastructure. Furthermore, the study informed on additional data that would be valuable to collect to enhance bikeability assessments for schools and other child-centric areas. For instance, while the current cycling network and the respective *Cykelstråk* dataset may reflect bikeability for existing adult cyclists, their applicability to children might be limited. Making cycling more accessible to children—and potentially other vulnerable users—requires designing infrastructure tailored to the needs of children and other intended users while also considering guardians' perceptions, as they primarily determine their children's travel choices.

5.2. Limitations and future work

The study also has several limitations that could be addressed in future work. Firstly, the incorporation of indicators in the index was not validated beforehand, as seen in studies such as Lee et al. (2020). However, the index accounted for the majority of commonly used physical-environment indicators in bikeability studies, as identified in a systematic review of bikeability research (Valenzuela et al., 2022) and studies on barriers to active commuting to school (Aranda-Balboa et al., 2020). One commonly mentioned factor omitted in this study was land use mix. Although the evidence on its impact is mixed and inconsistent, as discussed in 2.2, it could be beneficial to examine it in this context. Future studies could also improve the index by incorporating additional data that were currently omitted due to their unavailability. These factors, including lightning and the width of bike paths, both possibly affecting safety, could provide more nuanced results. This study did not

aim to model school mode choice, as done in studies such as Macedo et al. (2023). To do so, additional indicators would need to be incorporated, including households attitudes, norms, socio-demographic characteristics, and mobility options. Moreover, reducing the number of guardians driving their children to school requires discouraging car use, which necessitates not only improved cycling infrastructure but also broader, non-infrastructure-related interventions (McDonald and Aalborg, 2009).

Secondly, to maintain simple operationalization, the study did not account for possible interactions or cross-effects between multiple indicators. For example, the presence of greenery can have a positive impact if well-maintained but it may negatively affect bikeability if poorly managed (Krenn et al., 2015). A well-connected network of bicycle-friendly streets increases comfort and safety (Yang et al., 2019); simultaneously, increased street connectivity may lead to more unprotected intersections, reducing overall safety. Similarly, the presence of cycling paths may have varying effects. For example, high cyclist volumes on certain paths could create barriers for children cycling to school, as the behaviour of other users might be perceived as reckless or unsafe. This issue could be particularly pronounced in areas where cycling mode share has recently increased, but infrastructural adaptations have been slow to follow (Gustafsson and Archer, 2013). Moreover, the impact of certain indicators may vary depending on whether the environment we consider is near the school or the home (Macedo et al., 2023; Mitra et al., 2010). Although, distances to primary schools are generally relatively short enough to minimise large discrepancies, future survey designs could explicitly ask respondents about different sections of school routes to better capture these spatial variations.

Thirdly, a pilot study to validate the survey used to collect the indicator weights was not done due to time constraints to and the need to distribute the survey before the start of the summer holidays, during

which both guardians and school administrations would have limited availability. The survey, however, followed a standard Likert-scale format to capture preferences, with accompanying photos to enhance clarity. The found variations in scores across different indicators, as captured by the survey, although warrant further examination. Unfortunately, it was difficult to provide a closer comparison with another study to assess validity of this study as a similar study focusing on adult bikeability in Stockholm or children's bikeability in other areas of Sweden does not, to the authors' knowledge, exist. Given the relatively small sample size, which was skewed toward female participants and potentially guardians with children in lower school grades, it would be beneficial to aim to repeat a similar survey with a larger and more evenly distributed sample. It was also not specified whether both guardians of one child could fill the survey, or only one of them. While this does not seem to have significantly influenced the results, as each guardian had their own perceptions, a clarification regarding this could have been added in the survey. In this study, no distinction was also made between children cycling alone, or with their guardians, siblings or friends. It could be interesting to make this distinction in the future.

Fourthly, this study relied solely on spatial data to measure accessibility and, apart from incorporating indicator weights, did not account for individual perceptions. As previous research has suggested, perceptions—particularly of safety—influence parents' decisions on whether to allow their children to cycle (Hume et al., 2009; Wangzom et al., 2023; Westman et al., 2017). Therefore, an extension of this study could account for perceived bikeability. Further, habits, attitudes, and a positive and encouraging social environment could be included (Aranda-Balboa et al., 2020; Carver et al., 2014; McMillan, 2005; Mitra, 2013).

Fifthly, this study constructed a single index, with weights determined by guardians' preferences. Although there is evidence indicating that parents are the primary decision-makers, especially for younger children, incorporating children's perspectives—particularly for older children—could provide a valuable addition. The discrepancy between guardians' and children's perspectives is evident for example, in findings showing that while parents reported allowing more than half of children to cycle on busy roads from the age of thirteen, children themselves indicated that this occurred as early as from the age of ten (Björklid and Gummesson, 2013). Alternatively, a different weighting methods could be implemented; for instance, deriving weights through a binary discrete choice analysis, as demonstrated by Arellana et al. (2020).

Lastly, the income inequality analysis in this study was short. A more comprehensive equity analysis of school bikeability could be achieved by incorporating individual-level characteristics, which may offer deeper insights into how accessibility differs among social groups.

5.3. Conclusion

This study introduced a novel, child-focused School Bikeability Index for assessing the bicycle accessibility of primary schools in Stockholm. The index revealed significant variability in bikeability across school areas and identified key indicators that can be targeted for improvement, including bicycle parking, speed limiting measures, and child-friendly bicycle infrastructure. While several limitations related to survey design, indicator selection, and generalisability were acknowledged, the findings demonstrate the index's potential to inform more inclusive and effective planning. Future studies that integrate children's perspectives, perceived accessibility, and more nuanced spatial indicators can further enhance the applicability and impact of the index in supporting safe, independent, and active school travel.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Fariya Sharmeen: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Ivana Paulusová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT in order to improve the readability and language of the final manuscript. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Ivana Paulusova reports writing assistance was provided by WSP Sverige. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jcmr.2025.100074](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcmr.2025.100074).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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